

QISQA TUTASHUV NATIJASIDA ELEKTR QURLIMANING YONG'INGA
BARDOSHLILIK HISOBI.

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Annotatsiya: Qisqa tutashuv natijasida elektr qurlimaning yong'inga bardoshlilik hisobi aniqlash. Elektro energiya istimolchilari tarmoqqa birdaniga ulanmaydi. Buning ustiga dvigatellar hamma vaqt to'la yuklash bilan ishlayvermaydi. Shuning uchun hisoblashda o'rnatilgan kilovvat emas, uning istemolchi tomonidan birdaniga foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan qismi nazarga olinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qisqa tutashuv, hisoblagich, qurilma, bardoshlilik

Hisoblangan quvvatning o'rnatilgan quvvatga nisbatan talab koeffitsenti deyiladi. Bunda: P_h va I_h – birdaniga foydalanishi mumkin bo'lgan (hisoblangan) quvvat yoki tok; P_o va I_o – o'rnatilgan quvvat yoki tok; K_m – talab koeffitsenti.

Yoritish yuklamalari uchun talab koeffitsenti:

1. Tashqi yoritish tarmoqlari uchun $K_m=1$
2. Ro'zg'ordagi yoritish tarmoqlari uchun $K_m=0.7-0.8$
3. Sanoat korxonalarini tarmoqlari uchun $K_m=0.7-0.9$
4. Uzoq vaqt davomida ishlaydigan dvigatellar uchun $K_m=0.8$

Ko'tarish mexanizmlarida ishlaydigan dvigatellar soni 1 dan 5 gacha bo'lsa $K_m=0.8$; 5 dan 10 gacha bo'lsa $K_m=0.65$, dastgohlarda o'rnatilgan va takroriy qisqa muddatli rejimda ishlaydigan dvigatellar uchun 1 dan 5 gacha $K_m=0.8$, 5 dan 10 gacha $K_m=0.5$

Bir foizli o'zgaruvchan va o'zgarmas tarmoqlar uchun yoritish yuklanishida hisob qilingan tok:

$$I_x = \frac{K_m \cdot P_y}{U} = \frac{P_x}{U}. \quad (1)$$

Uch fazali tok zanjiri uchun:

$$I_x = \frac{K_m \cdot P_y}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U} = \frac{P_x}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U}. \quad (2)$$

O'zgarmas tok dvigatelining nominal toki:

$$I_n = \frac{P_n}{U \cdot \eta} \quad (3)$$

Uch fazali dvigatelning nominal toki:

$$I_H = \frac{P_n}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U \cdot \cos \varphi \cdot h} \quad (4)$$

η -elektor dvigatelining foydali ish ko'effitsenti.

Dvigatellar uchun va ning qiymatlari ma'lumotnomalar va kataloglardan olinadi. Tahminiy hisoblashlarda 10-12 kVt gacha kichik quvvatli dvigatellar uchun $\eta \cdot \cos \varphi$ ko'paytma qattiqligi 0.7:0.8 ga teng deb olinishi mumkin.

$$I_x = K_m \cdot I_n = K_m \cdot I_y \quad (5)$$

Simlarning kesim yuzasi ular uchun yo'l qo'yiladigan qizishga ko'ra jadvaldan aniqlanadi. Jadvalda uzoq muddatli yo'l qo'yiladigan tok uchun standart kesimlari berilgan.

Simlarda yo'l qo'yiladigan tok hisoblanadigan tokdan kichik bo'lmasligi kerak, ya'ni:

$$I_{yq} \geq I_h \quad (6)$$

I_{yq} -yo'l qo'yilgan tok.

Saqlag'larning eruvchan qo'yilmalarini tanlash

Saqlagichlarning eruvchan qo'yilmalarning vazifasi simlarning qisqa tutashuv toklaridan va katta ortiqcha yuklanishdan saqlashdir. Hisoblash tokidan katta toklar o'tganida eruvchan quyma quyib ketishi kerak.

Eruvchan quymaning normal toki I_{quy} liniyani himoya qilayotgan hisoblash tokiga teng yoki undan katta bo'lishi kerak, ya'ni:

$$I_{quy} \geq I_h \quad (6^*)$$

Bitta dvigatel uchun eruvchan quymaning nominal toki quyidagicha hisoblanadi.

A) dvigatelning nominal tok bo'yicha:

$$I_{quy} \geq \alpha I_{nom} \quad (7)$$

B) yurgazish toki bo'yicha

$$I_{kuy} \geq \frac{I_{no}}{\beta} = \frac{K_I \cdot I_{nom}}{\beta} \quad (8)$$

Bundan: I_{nom} - dvigatelning normal toki, I_{yu} -dvigatelning yurgazish toki, α -dvigatelning ish rejimiga bog'liq ko'effitsenti (uzoq muddatli rejim uchun $\alpha=1$, takroriy $\alpha=1.25$ muddat rejimi uchun $\alpha=1.25$).

β -yurgazish sharoitini belgilaydigan ko'effitsenti (normal sharoitda $\beta=2.5$, og'ir sharoitda $\beta=(1.6-2)$, K_i -yurgazish tokining karraliligi).

Ishlayotgan bir guruh dvigatellar uchun eruvchan quymaning toki

$$I_{kuy} = \frac{\sum I_{nom. \text{ dan}} + (I_{no} - I_{nom})}{2.5} \quad (9)$$

Bunda: $\sum I_{nom.}$ - birdaniga ishlaydigan dvigatellar nominal toklarining yig'indisi.

$I_{yu} - I_{nom}$ -dvigatelni yurgazish toki va nominal toklar farqi.

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